

Factors Influencing Academic Adjustment and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education Institutions in Battambang: A Conceptual Framework

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Abstract:

University students frequently encounter comparable difficulties and experiences during the transition process, both domestically and internationally. Navigating academic adjustment successfully necessitates effectively addressing a number of variables that affect how effective the learning results are. The purpose of this study is to provide a conceptual framework, as well as to discover and elucidate the complex relationship between one mediated factor that influences students' learning outcomes and five predictor variables that influence how well students adjust academically. The independent variables include individual factors (INF), instructional and school factors (ISF), social and cultural factors (SCF), mental

factors (MEF), and academic attainment factors (AAF). The mediated variable is the success of academic adjustment (SAA), and the dependent variable is the student's learning outcome (SLO). This study entails a thorough review of data sources such as academic journals, research papers, and empirical studies from 1990--2024. The findings reveal that INF, ISF, SCF, MEF, and AAF directly influence and that positive relationships with SAA and SAA directly influence SLO. This research integrates theoretical perspectives and empirical evidence to propose a cohesive model that can guide future research and provide insight into effective educational practices. Students at higher education institutions in Battambang benefit from a more supportive learning environment created by a comprehensive approach that includes these components. This will also help students adjust academically and improve their learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Academic adjustment, higher education institution, learning outcome, students.*

Introduction

Education's primary purpose is to preserve history alongside adapting to a modern world,

giving future generations educational and cultural assets, which they need to address the issues they face. For Cambodia's social economy and human capital to flourish, education is

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essential. Education is desperately needed to actively respond to the rapidly changing labor markets in the 21st century, both nationally and internationally (Malik, 2018). Moreover, political unrest has a significant effect on the educational system in Cambodia. For example, the education system in Cambodia has undergone several changes: initially established as the 4+3+3 system in 1979, it was modified to the 5+3+3 system following the fall of the Khmer Rouge, and most recently, it transitioned to the 6+3+3 system in 1996, comprising six years of primary education, three years of lower secondary education, and three years of upper secondary education (Moeurn, 2017; Em et al., 2022; Tieng et al., 2023; MoEYS, 2024).

The current Cambodian educational system consists of four levels: preschool, primary education, secondary education (lower and upper), and higher education (Benveniste et al., 2008; Chhinh & Dy, 2009; Sam et al. 2013a; Sam et al., 2013b). The Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC) ensures that Cambodians complete grades of at least 9 by providing basic education. Education in Cambodia can be delivered in three forms: formal, nonformal, and informal. The formal education structure includes early childhood education (grades 1--6), lower secondary school (grades 7--9), and upper secondary school (grades 10--12). Typically, students continue their education at a university rather than complete Technical Vocational Education and Training, or TVET (Chea, 2021; Sothy & Madhur, 2015.p.p-31.33).

At the tertiary level, the increasing number of higher education institutions in Cambodia reflects a significant increase in the number of high school graduates enrolling in college. During the 2002--2003 academic year, 16 new private higher education institutions were founded, and by 2003--2004, total enrollment in higher education institutions reached 45,000 students, with 40% of these students attending private institutions (Sovachana, 1991). By the 2012--2013 academic year, the number of university students had grown to 255,791 (Sothy & Madhur, 2015). Currently, 189 universities in Cambodia are overseen by 17 ministries and one secretariat, and they are distributed across 20

provinces and Phnom Penh. This total includes 79 public and 110 private universities. Remarkably, the annual higher education enrollment in Cambodia more than doubled between 2003 and 2023, rising from 14,778 to 284,599 students (MoEYS, 2023).

Either an associate degree or a satisfactory completion of Grade 12 is the prerequisite for pursuing postsecondary education in Cambodia. Students are not eligible for higher education if they do not meet one of these requirements (Sam et al., 2012 a; Sam et al., 2012 b; Sen & Ros, 2013.p.16; Chealy, 2009). Students need to maintain a strong academic record, as it reflects their abilities and potential. Research has shown that access to resources significantly influences students' academic performance (Adeniran, 2020).

Despite the substantial and noticeable increase in annual enrollment rates, several studies have indicated that significant dropout rates persist and are influenced by various factors that impact higher education institutions, particularly undergraduate students (Ozcan, 2021; Yan & Chea, 2024). These factors encompass individual attributes, social and cultural influences, health, instructional methods, the school environment, and academic achievements, which may not always align with students' ease and satisfaction in adapting and adjusting.

In particular, there has been little prior research on academic adjustment in tertiary students in Cambodia, while extensive studies have been conducted worldwide. Using widely recognized research models created by eminent researchers (Antonenko, 2015) is the goal of this study, which involves conceptualizing the various factors that influence students' success in academic adjustment. Research indicates that several elements significantly impact students' ability to adapt successfully to their academic lives. Six components in particular are recognized as positively influencing academic adjustment success and are hypothesized to do so: individual, instructional and school, mental, and academic attainment factors and the success of academic adjustment.

Purposes of the Study

This conceptual work aims to propose, identify, and clarify the key predictive factors affecting academic adjustment (SAA) and to explore how SAA mediates students' learning outcomes (SLOs) at higher education institutions in Battambang. The study seeks to illuminate the complex interplay between these predictive and mediating factors and their influence on academic adjustment and learning outcomes. By synthesizing existing research and theoretical frameworks, this study aims to clarify the dynamics of SAA within the educational context of the Battambang region. Ultimately, this research intends to enhance the understanding of how successful academic adjustment impacts learning outcomes, thereby informing future research and contributing to effective educational practices.

Research Question

How do the primary predictive factors—individual (INF), instructional and school (ISF), social and cultural (SCF), mental (MEF), and academic (AAF) attainment—influence student learning outcomes (SLO) through the mediating factor of the success of academic adjustment (SAA) among students at higher education institutions in Battambang? Additionally, how do these factors interact to collectively enhance students' academic outcomes, and what are the correlations between these factors?

Research Method

This conceptual work aims to conduct a comprehensive review and compilation of the available data sources. These sources encompass academic journals, open-access information repositories, research papers, systematic reviews, instructional materials, and empirical studies. The objective is to meticulously collect and analyze a broad range of scholarly and practical studies to propose a conceptual framework. This thorough synthesis of diverse data sources and information from documents from 1990–2024 provides a strong foundation for investigating the factors influencing the success of academic adjustment and student learning outcomes of

students in higher education institutions in Battambang.

Literature Review

Academic Adjustment Theoretical Models

Academic adjustment for tertiary students is influenced by various theoretical models, each emphasizing different aspects of the shift to higher education. The theoretical framework of academic adjustment proposed by Tinto (1975) serves as the foundation for comprehending student achievement in higher education. The model comprises three main components: academic integration, social integration, and goal commitment. First, academic integration pertains to a student's academic performance and intellectual growth (Confrey, 1994). The second is social integration, which involves interactions with peers and faculty (Dean et al., 2020). Third, goal commitment is the degree to which a student is dedicated to completing their educational objectives (Harackiewicz et al., 1998).

Academic Integration

Academic integration, according to Tinto's model, is pivotal for student success in higher education institutions. Herbaut (2021) emphasized that students with strong educational skills and knowledge are more likely to succeed in completing their studies, thereby underscoring the importance of adequate preparation before entering higher education. Similarly, constructivist learning theory, articulated by Piaget (1977) and Vygotsky (1978), highlights the need for active engagement with the environment for knowledge construction, necessitating effective participation and communication in collaborative settings for first-year students. Additionally, the technology acceptance model (TAM) by Davis (1989) explains students' reluctance in using ICT and digital content, noting that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness play crucial roles in determining the acceptance and use of technology and that effective use of ICT can enhance academic achievement (Yu et al., 2023; Basri et al., 2018; Malik, 2018; Karamti, 2016).

Furthermore, effective teaching that incorporates collaborative and interactive learning methods can significantly enhance students' academic adjustment (Lombard, 2020). Consequently, based on social learning theory (Bandura, 1977), Pedro et al. (2018) revealed that faculty quality and teaching methods play crucial roles in influencing freshmen's ability to adapt.

Social Integration

Tinto's social integration model is fundamental to enhancing student retention and academic success within higher education institutions. Durkheim's model (1961) suggests that insufficient social integration can lead to dropout behavior and that students who lack adequate integration into a college's social systems may experience low commitment and a greater likelihood of dropping out. Similarly, Bandura (1977) emphasized observational learning, imitation, and modeling, where engaging in study groups and academic communities can improve academic performance (Brandl et al., 2017) through shared learning and support of Lave and Wenger's model (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Additionally, Cohen and Wills (1985) propose social support theory (SST). The theory suggests that social support acts as a protective buffer against stress and that freshmen with strong social networks are more likely to cope effectively with the challenges of higher education. Perceived social support has been found to be a significant predictor of both social adjustment and academic achievement among university students (Sam et al., 2024; Maqbool et al., 2021). This suggests that students who perceive strong support networks from peers, family, and the university community (Maunder, 2018; Altermatt, 2019) are more likely to adapt successfully to the social environment of higher education.

Moreover, these students tend to perform better academically. The availability of emotional and practical support can alleviate stress (Beanlands, 2019), foster a sense of belonging, and enhance motivation, which collectively contribute to improved academic outcomes and smoother social transitions in the university setting. The

study also emphasized the importance of educational institutions building strong support networks and relationships with students to enhance student achievement. Additionally, Tajfel and Turner (1979) demonstrated through their social identity theory that people's behavior and sense of belonging to social groups influence their self-esteem, suggesting that a strong sense of belonging can improve social integration and academic success (Strayhorn, 2018).

Goal Commitment

Through Tinto's model, a strong commitment to goals is vital for achieving academic success in higher education. Theory of Caplan's person-environment fit (Caplan, 1987) posits that the alignment between an individual's traits and their environment strongly affects their well-being and performance, emphasizing that attributes such as stress management and time management skills are critical for academic adaptation (Purnamasari et al., 2022; DeVilbiss, 2014). Similarly, Bandura's theory of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997) highlights the importance of individuals' confidence in their ability to succeed in specific situations, with high self-efficacy linked to better academic outcomes and goal commitment (Sabela et al., 2022; Lipka et al., 2020). Furthermore, Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Maslow, 1943) asserts that basic needs such as financial stability must be satisfied before individuals can pursue higher-level objectives such as academic success, as financial stress can adversely affect academic adjustment (Chea, 2015; Bernier et al., 2004). Additionally, Barney's resource-based approach (Barney, 1991) suggests that access to valuable resources, including institutional support services, can improve performance, with the effective use of resources such as libraries and academic support centers being essential for academic achievement (Willems et al., 2022). Moreover, Eccles et al. (1983), through expectancy-value theory, proposed that students' motivation and achievement are influenced by their expectations of success and the value they assign to academic tasks (Offidani-Bertrand et al., 2022), although some studies contend that there is no direct link between class achievement and motivation (Sujana et al., 2021; Lakhani et al., 2017).

Individual Factors (INF) Related to SAA

Individual factors (INFs) pertain to personal attributes that significantly influence a student's academic adjustment. These attributes include motivation (Iqbal et al., 2023; Kew et al., 2018), which can be classified into extrinsic and intrinsic types. Intrinsic motivation is characterized by an internal drive to learn and succeed, charged by personal satisfaction and genuine inquiry into the topic (Kyndt et al., 2015; Deci & Ryan, 2000). However, a need to do things for their own sake is a sign of extrinsic motivation to achieve external rewards rather than inherent satisfaction or interest. A common incentive for this type of motivation is ambition for high grades (Ogbonnaya et al., 2023), the pursuit of recognition and approval from others, and aspirations for future career opportunities (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

For students, extrinsic motivation can play an essential part in academic performance, as the anticipation of tangible rewards leads to increased effort and persistence in their studies (Khaliq et al., 2023; Schunk et al., 2008). However, while extrinsic rewards can effectively motivate students in the short term, they might not always promote long-term engagement, including deep learning (Deci et al., 1991).

The concept of self-efficacy, which is the conviction that one can succeed in particular circumstances or complete a task, is essential to a student's academic transition. People with strong self-efficacy are more likely to be associated with emotion and to show greater tenacity and resilience when faced with academic challenges (Keller et al. 2024; Bandura, 1997). This is a result of their belief that challenges can be conquered and their ongoing motivation to do so via perseverance and hard work. Greater self-confidence in students can result in improved academic achievement because they are more likely to create and stick to ambitious objectives and bounce back quickly from setbacks (Yi et al., 2024; Fenollar et al., 2007; Zimmerman, 2000).

Students who have a high sense of their own efficacy also have faith in their capacity to complete assignments. This self-assurance can

lower anxiety, improve one's capacity for problem solving, and motivate proactive learning. Consequently, it is probable that these students will transition to the academic setting more readily (Ivemark & Ambrose, 2021; Barker, 2007), which will enhance their academic achievement (Madson et al., 2022).

Learning styles, which refer to the preferred ways individuals receive and process information, significantly influence the success of academic adjustment. Students exhibit diverse learning styles, such as kinesthetic, auditory, visual, written, and reflective (Ghobain & Zughaihi, 2024), as well as pragmatist, theorist, activist, and reflection (Yousef, 2018). These styles affect how they interact with the curriculum and teaching strategies (Fleming & Mills, 1992). For example, whereas auditory learners thrive when listening to lectures and discussions, visual learners gain from charts, diagrams, and other graphical representations, including assessments and evaluative tests (Sayed et al., 2024). Kinesthetic students benefit from hands-on exercises and experiments, whereas reading/writing learners enjoy text-based activities such as reading textbooks and taking notes (Pashler et al., 2008). Academic adjustment can be facilitated when instructional strategies consider the learning styles of students. This is because such strategies can enhance comprehension, retention, and application of knowledge (Li et al., 2021; Pashler et al., 2008; Felder & Brent, 2005).

In summary, the hypothesized relationships between individual factors and the success of academic adjustment are multifaceted outcomes. These outcomes collectively underscore the importance of addressing individual factors to promote successful academic adjustment. In short, individual factors (INFs) play a critical role in the success of academic adjustment (SAA). By fostering motivation, self-efficacy, and accommodating diverse learning styles, educational institutions can enhance students' ability to adapt to the academic environment, leading to successful learning outcomes.

Proposition 1: Individual factors positively influence the success of academic adjustment.

Instructional and School Factors for SAA

According to Murkatik et al. (2020), teacher competency includes both subject matter mastery and the capacity to use efficient instructional strategies. We investigate the vital role that teacher competence plays in affecting the success of academic adjustment, with a focus on the element of teaching quality as the essential component of successful teacher characteristics and school competency (Sofyan et al., 2023). Empirical studies have continuously demonstrated the significance of informed and personable educators in supporting their students' academic transition (Amirian et al., 2023). For example, Hattie (2009) reported that when students believe that their professors are competent and encouraging, they typically perform better academically. According to a study by Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), educators who use reflective teaching techniques and participate in ongoing professional development greatly improve the educational experiences of their students.

Furthermore, it is critical for educators to establish welcoming and stimulating classroom settings. According to Vangrieken et al. (2017), students' academic and social adjustment can be greatly improved by collaborative teaching strategies that encourage a feeling of community and active engagement (Xu, 2024). These methods enhance students' comprehension of the subject topic while also promoting their general wellbeing and school environment integration. Therefore, instructors' skills and approachability (Bell, 2022), which are supported by continual professional growth and teamwork, are crucial in helping children succeed academically.

Using a variety of interesting teaching techniques is essential. By addressing different learning styles, these tactics improve student engagement and promote better academic adjustment (Sanger, 2020, p. 37; Robiah et al., 2024). By meeting the needs of each individual student, Marzano (2003) indicated that using a range of

instructional methods can considerably increase learning outcomes. Differentiated instruction is highlighted by Patel (2020) and Tomlinson & Moon (2013), who stress that academic achievement and improved engagement result from adjusting teaching strategies to the varied talents and interests of students. In addition to catering to each student's individual learning style, differentiated education keeps students engaged and motivated—two things that are essential for their academic transition. Furthermore, the incorporation of technology into educational methodologies has yielded encouraging outcomes. Chen et al. (2020) and Mosenson & Johnson (2008, p. p-175.195) claim that the use of digital technologies and online resources produces dynamic, interactive learning environments that pique students' curiosity and inspire them. Immediate feedback and individualized learning experiences are provided by these technologically advanced methods, which are critical for students' academic adjustment.

This perspective is supported by recent research, which emphasizes the importance of curriculum rigor and relevance. Curricula that link academic information to real-world contexts, according to Darling-Hammond et al. (2019) and Tang (2020), not only help students learn more meaningfully but also aid in the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities (Leasa et al., 2020). According to Thomas (2009), this strategy ensures that students understand the importance of their education outside of the classroom, which increases student engagement and academic accomplishment.

In addition to relevance and rigor, the flexibility of the curriculum is essential in supporting individual learning needs and contributing to academic success. Ahmed et al. (2019) and Tomlinson (2001) revealed that flexible curricular structures that allow for student choice and differentiation can accommodate diverse learning preferences and styles, which improves academic performance. Teachers can create a more hospitable and encouraging learning atmosphere by giving students choices and allowing them to follow their interests

within the parameters of the curriculum (Lakkala et al., 2021). Moreover, contemporary studies underscore the benefits of a flexible curriculum. Rittle-Johnson et al. (2020) reported that adaptive curricula that respond to students' progress and provide personalized learning pathways significantly improve student involvement and achievement. This adaptability ensures that the curriculum is tailored to each student's specific needs, which fosters a sense of competence and autonomy that is essential for academic adjustment (Maddens et al., 2023).

Extracurricular activities help students better assimilate into their academic environment. According to Eccles and Barber (1999), involvement in extracurricular activities fosters a sense of community and belonging among students, which is associated with better academic performance and a greater drive to succeed (Ribeiro et al., 2023). Additionally, extracurricular activities provide students with opportunities to explore interests and develop new skills. Research by Dotterer et al. (2007) and Chapman et al. (2023) indicates that students who engage in extracurricular activities exhibit higher levels of academic motivation, improved time-management skills, and a stronger commitment to their educational goals—all of which are essential for effective academic adjustment.

Recent studies emphasize how important a supportive school climate is. Cohen et al. (2009) claim that academic achievement and student involvement are greater in schools that foster a positive school climate where collaboration, respect, and trust are valued. According to Fantus and Newman (2021), a supportive atmosphere fosters a sense of community among students, which is essential for both their academic and general well-being. Furthermore, academic advice and support services are essential for helping students navigate their academic paths, providing individualized help, and developing the skills necessary for academic success (McGillivray & Gilding, 2018).

In the hypothesis that ISF, particularly through access to learning materials and counseling services, significantly influences SAA, it is clear

that providing students with the necessary resources and support is essential for their academic adjustment and success.

Proposition 2: Instructional and School Factors significantly influence the Success of Academic Adjustment

Social and Cultural Factors for SAA

Social interactions and cultural backgrounds, including peer influence, family support, and socioeconomic status, significantly impact students' academic adjustment and outcomes (Baumert et al., 2024). Peer influence can either positively or negatively affect academic performance and adjustment (Chen et al., 2023). Positive peer interactions, support networks, and social support are associated with higher levels of engagement, motivation, and academic performance (Maqbool et al. 2021; Wentzel, 2017). On the other hand, unfavorable peer pressure can cause disengagement and problems in the classroom.

Another important component of academic adjustment is family support. According to research by Hill and Tyson (2009), there is a strong correlation between better academic achievement and adjustment and parental involvement in education, which is defined as monitoring, assistance, and encouragement (Chaudhary & Garg, 2023). Students are more likely to develop favorable attitudes toward school, show better study habits, and achieve greater academic results when families actively participate in their children's education (Lv et al., 2019).

Academic adjustment is also significantly influenced by socioeconomic status (SES). Higher SES students frequently have greater access to advanced learning materials, extracurricular activities, and private tutoring, all of which can improve their academic performance and achievement (Munir et al., 2023). In contrast, children from poorer socioeconomic situations could face difficulties such as restricted resource availability, financial strain, and less parental support for their academic work (Lopez, 2023). The achievement gap between high- and low-SES students is a

chronic problem, as shown by Rodríguez-Hernández et al. (2020) and Reardon (2011), with socioeconomic disparities contributing to discrepancies in academic results and adjustments (Gao et al., 2021).

Current studies further highlight the interplay of social and cultural factors in academic adjustment. Raver et al. (2013) and Danner et al. (2021) reported that socioemotional skills, which are often influenced by social and cultural contexts, are critical for academic success. These skills include self-regulation, empathy, and effective communication (Zimmerman, 1989), all of which are essential for navigating the academic environment.

Cultural background also shapes students' academic experiences. Aldayel (2020) and Chiu & Chow (2010) reported that cultural values, beliefs, and practices can influence students' attitudes toward education, learning styles, and academic aspirations. For example, students from cultures that highly value education and academic achievement may be more motivated and persistent in their studies (Boyle et al., 2020), leading to better academic adjustment.

To be proposed as influencing factors on the success of academic adjustment (SAA), it is evident that social interactions, family support, and socioeconomic status are critical components in determining and contributing to students' academic adjustment.

Proposition 3: Social and cultural factors contribute positively to the success of academic adjustment

Mental Factors for SAA

Mental factors (MEFs) shape students' psychological resilience, emotional regulation, and general well-being, which in turn influences the effectiveness of academic adjustment (SAA). Students' ability to overcome academic obstacles and fulfill their educational objectives is largely dependent on psychological factors, such as stress levels, mental health, and emotional intelligence (Sam et al., 2024; Cortés-Denia et al., 2020). Academic performance and cognitive functioning can be severely impacted by high levels of academic stress (Safriani & Muhid,

2022). For example, Feld and Shusterman (2015) reported that high levels of stress negatively impact children's ability to remember, focus, and solve problems, which impedes their ability to adjust to school. On the other hand, students who are adept at handling stress have an advantage in regard to studying and succeeding academically (Beanlands et al., 2019).

Mental health is another pivotal component of MEF. Anxiety and sadness are two mental health conditions that can seriously impair a student's capacity to cope with the demands of the classroom. Research by Hasanah et al. (2022) and Eisenberg et al. (2016) shows that mental health issues are common in college students and strongly affect their learning outcomes and academic performance. Conley et al. (2015), for example, reported that school-based mental health treatments enhance students' psychological well-being, which in turn promotes improved academic performance and adjustment.

Particularly important in influencing how successfully adolescents adjust to academic circumstances is emotional intelligence (EI). Pupils with high emotional intelligence are more adept at handling stress, understanding and controlling their emotions, and forming wholesome bonds with teachers and peers. Emotional intelligence is a strong predictor of academic performance because it promotes resilience, motivation, and good interpersonal abilities (MacCann et al., 2020; Ullah et al., 2023). These qualities are necessary for succeeding in the classroom and reaching long-term learning objectives. A body of recent research highlights the connection between academic adjustment and psychological well-being. For example, a meta-analysis conducted by Richardson et al. (2012) and Suleman et al. (2019) revealed that psychological factors—such as emotional intelligence, mental health, and stress management—have a major impact on students' academic adjustment.

The incorporation of mental health education into the curriculum can also improve students' understanding and coping mechanisms. According to Weare & Nind (2011) and Kassie

(2023), integrating social and emotional learning (SEL) programs into classrooms can enhance students' academic performance, social skills, and mental well-being. These courses help students learn stress management techniques, emotional intelligence development, responsible commitment and decision-making, and healthy relationship building—all of which are necessary for a successful academic transition (Demirci et al., 2022).

In summary, MEFs, which encompass psychological aspects such as stress levels, mental health, and emotional intelligence, are vital for students' academic adjustment and success. Addressing these factors through comprehensive mental health support and education can significantly enhance students' ability to cope with academic challenges and achieve their adjustment.

Proposition 4: Mental factors have a significant effect on the success of academic adjustment

Academic Attainment Factors (AAF) toward SAA

Academic attainment factors (AAFs) are vital in understanding the success of academic adjustment (SAA), as they provide a foundational basis upon which future academic performance and adjustment are built. In accordance with Nabizadeh et al. (2019), there is a strong correlation between students' capacity to adjust to novel academic environments and obstacles and their prior academic accomplishments, grades, and scores on standardized tests. An investigation by Pascarella & Terenzini (2005) and Levi et al. (2014) revealed that students with a history of strong academic performance are more likely to display resilience, confidence, and productive study habits—all of which are necessary for a successful academic transition (De Clercq et al., 2017). Recent research underlines the role that the AAF plays in academic adjustment even more. Conley (2014) and Barros & Simão (2018) contend that students who have achieved academic success in the past are better equipped with internal and controllable abilities and knowledge that aid in their transition to higher

education. Because they are better equipped to handle the greater challenges of advanced coursework and more demanding academic standards, students with a background of strong academic accomplishment have an easier transition (Lin et al., 2023).

Standardized test scores are also a significant component of AAF. According to Geiser & Santelices (2007), standardized tests provide a measurable and comparative assessment of students' academic abilities, which can be used to predict their potential for success in future academic endeavors (Tikhomirova et al., 2020). These scores often reflect students' mastery of key concepts and skills, indicating their readiness for subsequent educational challenges.

In addition, prior academic accomplishments play a greater role than only grades and scores do. Duckworth et al. (2011) and Sever (2023) emphasized the importance of growth mindsets and academic tenacity, which are frequently fostered by prior academic experiences (Buzetto-Hollywood et al., 2019; Park et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2022). Prior accomplishments indicate that a student has probably developed resilience and a strong work ethic, two qualities that are critical for adjusting to new academic environments and managing the intricacies of higher education (Rios, 2019).

In summary, it is clear that previous academic achievements, grades, and standardized test scores are not only indicators of past performance but also key determinants of present academic success and adjustment in proposing the hypothesis that the AAF significantly influences SAA.

Proposition 5: Academic attainment factors positively influence the success of academic adjustment.

Success of Academic Adjustment (SAA) as a mediator of SLO

The success of academic adjustment (SAA) is a crucial mediating factor influencing student learning outcomes, encompassing various dimensions such as academic performance, retention rates, engagement, and satisfaction embedded in INF, ISF, SCF, MEF, and AAF.

SAA is a measure of how well a student has adapted to the classroom, which has a direct bearing on their academic performance. One of the main measures of how well students grasp the curriculum and meet learning objectives through tenacity and academic resilience is their academic performance, which is a fundamental aspect of student achievement assurance (SAA) (Ononye et al., 2022). According to research by Richardson et al. (2012) and Mushtaq & Khan (2012), academic adjustment plays a crucial role in determining educational results because it significantly predicts academic success.

Furthermore, there is a strong correlation between SAA and retention rates because students who successfully manage academic demands have higher retention rates (Rios, 2019). The importance of successful academic and social integration in the classroom has been highlighted by Tinto (2012), and research by Chamely Wiik et al. (2021) shows how the T-LEARNING model could be used in academic programs. These two findings lead to higher retention rates, illustrating the importance of SAA in preventing student attrition.

Students' active participation in class activities and dedication to learning are key components of engagement, which is another essential component of SAA. Higher levels of involvement have been linked to better academic outcomes (Sengsouliya et al., 2020; Myint & Khaing, 2020); Fredricks et al., 2004). This suggests that more engaged students are more likely to succeed academically.

Additionally, student satisfaction with their academic experience is a key component of SAA. Students' beliefs about the value and applicability of their education are reflected in their level of satisfaction, which has an impact on their motivation and general academic success. Dinh et al. (2021) reported that student satisfaction encompasses five aspects: the

educational environment, activities, educational outcomes, and the availability of facilities and teaching equipment. This further validates the role of SAA as a mediator of student learning outcomes. A study by Kuh et al. (2006) revealed that student satisfaction is positively correlated with both academic performance and retention.

The diverse characteristics of SAA and its wide-ranging effects on numerous facets of student success have also been highlighted in recent research. The findings of Komarraju et al. (2014) and Herdlein & Zurner (2015), for example, indicate that students view interactions outside of the classroom as valuable opportunities to develop and refine various personal knowledge and skill sets. These research papers also examine the role of self-efficacy and goal orientation in academic adjustment, suggesting that students with higher self-efficacy are more likely to adjust successfully and achieve positive learning outcomes. Similarly, studies conducted by Credé & Niehorster (2012) and Mustafa et al. (2020) show that academic adjustment mediates the link between academic achievement and psychological well-being, meaning that students with high academic achievement are typically well adjusted.

In essence, the success of academic adjustment (SAA) serves as a vital mediating factor influencing student learning outcomes. This influence is exerted through various dimensions, including INF, ISF, SCF, MEF, and AAF factors. These dimensions collectively impact critical aspects of the student experience, such as academic performance, retention rates, engagement levels, and overall satisfaction with the educational process.

Proposition 6: The success of academic adjustment (SAA) positively and significantly influences students' learning outcomes.

Figure 1. The Conceptualized Framework Model

Conclusion

The objective of this research was to determine and suggest the major variables affecting first-year students' success of academic adjustment (SAA) at higher education establishments in Battambang. A thorough analysis of research and theoretical frameworks led to the identification of various predictor variables, demonstrating the intricate interaction between mediated and predictive variables influencing students' learning outcomes (SLOs).

In conclusion, the success of academic adjustment (SAA) is a multifaceted mediator crucial for optimizing student learning outcomes (SLOs). Individual factors such as intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and alignment with learning styles significantly influence SAA by enhancing engagement and performance. SAA is further influenced by instructional and school features, such as supportive school settings,

diversified instructional methodologies, inclusive teaching practices, and competent teachers. Peer relationships, parental backing, socioeconomic level, and cultural background are examples of social and cultural elements that affect academic adjustment through influencing motivation and resource accessibility. Mental factors, such as stress management, mental health, and emotional intelligence, play critical roles in navigating academic challenges. Academic attainment factors, including past achievements and standardized test scores, provide a foundation for adjusting to new academic demands. Therefore, integrating strategies that address these diverse factors is essential for fostering successful academic adjustment and improving overall student learning outcomes.

To improve the success of academic adjustment (SAA) and student learning outcomes (SLO) in Battambang HEIs, an emphasis should be

placed on cultivating intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy through personalized advising and mentorship, enhancing instructional quality with faculty development and inclusive learning environments, addressing socioeconomic disparities and integrating culturally relevant practices, implementing mental health initiatives and social-emotional learning (SEL) programs, and tailoring support on the basis of academic attainment factors. A comprehensive strategy that integrates these elements will create a supportive educational environment and, in doing so, improve the academic adjustment and learning outcomes of students at higher education institutions in Battambang.

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Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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